

MOVING TOWARDS LIFE CYCLE THINKING BY INTEGRATING ADVANCED WASTE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

1 SOME DATA

- About 9% of the waste generated in the EU have residential origin
- 80 MTONs of recyclable materials are yearly wasted
- About 75% of food waste can be avoided

2 MAIN OBJECTIVE OF WASTE4THINK

The main objective of Waste4Think is **to move forward the current waste management practices into a circular economy motto** demonstrating the value of integrating and validating **20 eco-innovative solutions** that cover all the waste value chain. The benefits of these solutions will be enhanced by a **holistic waste data management methodology**, and will be demonstrated in **4 complementary urban areas in Europe**

3 CONSORTIUM

4 TIMING AND BUDGET

5 THE SOLUTIONS

- The solutions include technological and non-technological approaches as:
- **ICT tools** to support daily operation and long-term planning
 - **APPs** for citizen empowerment and engagement
 - **Educational materials** based on innovative teaching units and serious games
 - **Tools for citizen science** for the co-creation of novel solutions
 - Mechanisms to boost behavioural changes based on **economic instruments** and **social actions**
 - Decentralized solutions for **valorisation and reuse of high value resources**

6 EXPECTED IMPACT

Into a **virtual city that integrates the 20 eco-innovative solutions**

- **10% reduction** of GHG emissions
- **20% increment** of waste sorting
- **10% savings** in the management costs

Networking and synergetic collaboration among partners

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